

BUDGETARY TRENDS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION AND ITS MEMBER STATES AND IMPLICATIONS FOR CLIMATE FINANCE

POLICY BRIEF

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This brief examines the budgetary trends of the European Union (EU) and its 27 Member States from 2020 to 2025, and projects how trends through 2034 may affect international climate finance. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine, rising inflation, and global geopolitical tensions, EU and national budgets of Member States have increasingly shifted toward defence, energy security, and industrial competitiveness. As a result, climate finance risks being deprioritized, affecting the EU's ability to fulfill its obligations under the UNFCCC and Paris Agreement and support the scaling up of climate finance in line with the new collective quantified goal established at COP29.

At the EU level, the proposed new Multiannual Financial Framework sets record-high spending levels, yet a substantial portion is allocated to defence, strategic autonomy, and crisis-response initiatives rather than climate and development aid. The budget structure has been redesigned to be more flexible but also less transparent: previously ring-fenced climate or development funds have been merged into broader envelopes, making it increasingly difficult to track actual allocations to climate objectives. **At the national level, Member State budgets mirror these tendencies, with major donors cutting climate and development finance while sharply increasing defence expenditure.** Political priorities reflect this shift, as most governing parties across Europe now emphasize economic and security concerns over climate action.

The implications for international climate finance are significant, as bilateral climate-related finance is sharply declining. Although multilateral finance through Multilateral Development Banks is rising or being maintained, it fails to compensate for reductions in public finance. This is largely because it relies predominantly on non-grant instruments and disproportionately favors economically attractive sectors and regions. A clear paradox emerges: European Multilateral Development Banks, such as the European Investment Bank, are expanding their overall investment portfolios, yet most of the gains are retained within Europe, resulting in stagnation rather than growth in global climate-related support.

I. Introduction

The recognition of climate change as a defining global challenge of the 21st century, together with biodiversity loss and pollution, has been accompanied by a shifting geopolitical context, reshaping many political agendas and reordering priorities.

When urgent short-term crises dominate—whether they are sudden economic and public safety shocks or escalating geopolitical tensions—, long-term objectives are often relegated to the background. Among those longer-term goals, climate change stands out as the most pressing challenge, as its impacts accelerate while the window for effective action narrows.

For the European Union, action against climate change has been a key priority over the past few decades, first through initiatives such as the European Climate Change Programme (ECCP), the introduction of the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), or the 2050 Low-Carbon Roadmap. Later, with the European Green Deal and the adoption of the European Climate Law, EU institutions progressively integrated climate policy into their broader economic and digital strategy.

The war between Russia and Ukraine has fundamentally shifted priorities, **redirecting the EU's attention toward increased security and defence spending** alongside a heightened focus on securing energy supplies. Some examples of the war's catalyzation of major increases in defence spending include Germany's special EUR 100 billion fund, the EU's Peace Facility, and bolstered NATO commitments. **Simultaneously, concerns over economic competitiveness have intensified** in response to the 2022 United States' Inflation Reduction Act and China's push in green technology, prompting the EU to introduce the Net-Zero Industry Act and proposals for a Sovereignty Fund.

Experts warn that the decisions taken in this decade will set the course toward either a sustainable or a destructive path. According to the [Sixth Assessment Report](#) prepared by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), vulnerable populations, particularly those living in precarious conditions, are most exposed to the consequences of climate change while at the same time being the least responsible for historical emissions. While the medium-term economic and social impacts of climate change will be felt around the globe, climate vulnerability makes certain regions and populations more likely to be adversely affected.

The principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities (CBDR-RC) is fundamental to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Paris Agreement, recognizing that developed countries bear a greater responsibility for climate change and have an obligation to lead in climate action, including through the provision of finance to developing countries.

In the 2009 Copenhagen Accord, developed countries committed to a goal of jointly mobilizing USD 100 billion dollars a year by 2020 to address the needs of developing countries. This figure was never intended as a ceiling but rather as a baseline and a minimum floor for climate finance. Nevertheless, according to the OECD, the target was only reached in 2022, two years after the initial deadline. During COP29, Parties agreed on a **new collective quantified goal (NCQG) of at least USD 300 billion per year by 2035** for developing countries, with developed country Parties taking the lead in the provision of this financing. In addition, the NCQG also calls on all actors to work together to enable the scaling up of financing from all public and private sources to at least USD 1.3 trillion per year by 2035.

Climate finance, according to the UNFCCC Standing Committee on Finance, refers to finance that supports non-Annex I Parties in their efforts towards the reduction of emissions and the enhancement of greenhouse gas sinks, as well as measures that reduce vulnerability and build resilience of human and ecological systems to the impacts of climate change. It remains a contested concept, with no universally agreed methodology, resulting in varying scopes, approaches, and estimation techniques (e.g., methodologies applied by the [OECD](#), [MDBs](#), the [IDFC](#), or the [UNFCCC](#)). In this brief, climate finance is understood in the narrow sense of public funds provided through governmental budgets to support climate action, as opposed to financing as the notion of broader mobilization, or the process of mobilization, of resources from various sources, including private investment and capital markets. The following section will therefore focus specifically on public climate finance.

As highlighted in previous SLYCAN Trust reports, there is **a need to further raise the ambition of this new goal and work out its implementation modalities**, including through the Baku to Belém Roadmap to the overall funding target of USD 1.3 trillion. Key areas include enhancing access to and quality of climate finance, addressing systemic disenablers and barriers, and scaling up finance for adaptation and responding to loss and damage (L&D).

During COP29, several developing country representatives expressed that, while the decision on the NCQG can be seen as a step forward, it remains insufficient. Furthermore, the effectiveness of the financial target remains dependent on its effective implementation and political will.

Against the backdrop of the global climate change negotiations and a shifting geopolitical environment, this brief examines the EU and its Member States' budget allocations, and how changes in priorities might affect contributions or allocations to domestic as well as global public climate finance. By analyzing these trends, it aims to contribute to further exploring potential implications for meeting international climate targets and assessing whether the EU is on track to scale up its contributions.

II. EU budgetary trends and projections

The EU Multiannual Financial Framework

Objectives of the MFF Proposal: A Safe, Competitive, and Sovereign Europe

Neighbourhood and the World

Key findings:

- At the European level, the Commission has put forward a MFF proposal for 2028-2034, with a sharply increased focus on security and defence, competitiveness, and flexibility goals.
- Commission’s accountability is reduced by more generic financial programming, the removal of specific targets, and the merging of diverse expenditure categories. This would lead to a shift from ex ante oversight by the European Parliament and Council to ex post supervision.
- While it increases allocations for Global Europe, the main fund for climate-related aid to developing countries, the increase is less significant when accounting for inflation and category changes.
- Guiding principles for Global Europe are shifting from needs-based criteria to concepts such as shared priorities and strategic interests, reflecting a politicization of solidarity.

Under the slogan “A Strong Europe in a Changing World,” the 2025 Danish EU Presidency has outlined two overarching priorities: a secure Europe and a competitive and green Europe. The main focus areas include defence, support for Ukraine, EU enlargement, climate action, and economic competitiveness. The Presidency has stated that this multifaceted approach aims to strengthen EU defence capabilities and security architecture while promoting sustainable economic growth and advancing the green transition.

In July 2025, the European Commission published the long-anticipated Proposal for a Council Regulation laying down the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for 2028–2034. As established by Article 312 of the TFEU, this document determines the annual ceilings for both commitment and payment appropriations by category of expenditure. The MFF functions as an additional instrument to achieve EU objectives, allocating resources to different priorities. By law, the MFF must be laid down for a period of seven years. However, the current MFF Regulation covering the period 2021 to 2027 has already been revised twice since its adoption in 2020.

The two MFF revisions took place in 2022 in response to the outbreak of the Russia-Ukraine war and in June 2023 as a mid-term review of MFF implementation. The changes made as a result of the mid-term review exposed a distinct agenda that has recently been consolidated in the new MFF proposal. Amid ongoing geopolitical instability, this new proposal reflects a public declaration of the Commission’s policy intentions that remain to be validated by EU institutions. It proposes the largest budget in EU history with a total spending of EUR 2 trillion.

While the headline budget appears substantially higher, almost doubling the 2021-2027 figures, this increase is less significant than it initially appears. Although the higher figures suggest that more resources will be allocated, inflation-adjusted allocations and changes in categories indicate that the budget is not as extensive as it seems. Modifications in expenditure categories also make direct budget comparisons difficult. Based on an understanding of the term “climate finance” as explained above, the deeper analysis in this brief focuses on the external funding of the EU and its Member States.

i. Objectives of the MFF Proposal: A Safe, Competitive, and Sovereign Europe

As seen in the changes already implemented in the mid-term review, the Commission is emphasizing flexibility, simplification, and adaptability. **Following a prolonged period of successive crises, the EU is publicly betting on a more agile framework, seeking to streamline administrative processes and reduce red tape in the budget.** This effort is not unprecedented: similar proposals have been made in the past and were already contained in the mid-term review. The mid-term review strengthened budgetary flexibility through instruments such as the Solidarity and Emergency Aid Reserve. The Omnibus packages ([Omnibus I](#) released on 26 February 2025), meanwhile, were intended to enhance competitiveness by simplifying legal requirements for business and industry such as due diligence-related exigencies and reducing administrative costs.

Such amended proposals include the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), with changes such as reduced and postponed requirements for reporting. **However, while simplification promises efficiency, it also raises challenges.** The approach proposed by the Commission has several problematic aspects, including potential risks to democratic oversight, to the protection of core Union objectives, and to climate expenditure.

Simultaneously, the proposal intends to provide stronger, more focused public investment to support businesses and attract private funding.

Closely linked to the development of Europe’s defence sector, the proposal also envisions support for an independent Europe with its own strategic technologies and a powerful, and effective innovation and research framework. The total budget allocated to this mission surpasses the EUR 450 billion, out of which, around EUR 131 billion will be allocated to “Resilience and Security, Defence Industry, and Space”, aimed at strengthening Europe’s security capabilities and supporting critical infrastructure. **This represents a fivefold increase compared to the 2021-2027 period, which is complemented by increased allocations for military mobility and a larger cushion fund.** Cushion funds follow the previously outlined attempt to ensure flexibility, as they provide an emergency budget fund reserved to deal with unexpected expenses.

The new budget describes the **European Defence Union as “an urgent priority at a time of rising threats and uncertainty”** and announces the EU’s intention to take it to the “next level.” In order to achieve this, it calls for the joint development of critical European defence capabilities and further encourages Member States and regions to support investment in this field.

Figure 1: Comparison of MFF 2021-2027, MFF Mid-term Revision, and MFF Proposal 2028-2034.

Figure 2: European Peace Facility Funds (EUR million). Source: [European Council](#), (n.d)

This shift in priorities is reflected within the MFF proposal through instruments such as the Flexibility Mechanism or the Crisis Mechanism, and outside the MFF ceilings through off-budget tools such as the Ukraine Facility and the European Peace Facility. The latter has undergone three top-up modifications since March 2023, and its proposed budget for 2028-2034 is six times the amount established in 2021, clearly indicating a rising concern for the reinforcement of European security.

The connection between competitiveness and defence and security does not arise solely from the inclusion of defence-related items in the EU’s competitiveness budget. **Defence is portrayed both as a distinct objective in its own right and a means to enhance competitiveness, reflecting the EU’s broader strategy to establish Europe as a competitive player in the defence sector.** Boosting the agility and capabilities of the European defence industry is additionally intended to foster the emergence of new entrants and support industrial scale-up across the EU. As the MFF increasingly focuses on defence and competitiveness, climate and environmental objectives risk being deprioritized in funding, with potential implications for overall EU climate finance.

ii. Neighbourhood and the World

In the current MFF, the main instrument for climate finance is situated under the heading “Neighbourhood and the World,” which includes diverse instruments such as Humanitarian Aid and Pre-Accession Assistance (IPA). With a share of close to 72% of this heading, the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI) represents the EU’s primary tool for contributing to eradicating poverty, promoting sustainable development, and fostering prosperity, peace, and stability. One of the cross-cutting priorities of the instrument and its financial arm (the European Fund for Sustainable Development Plus, EFSD+) is the achievement of the EU’s international obligations, such as those enshrined under the Paris Agreement. Hence, the NDICI-Global Europe Regulation sets a target of 30 % of NDICI-Global Europe funds to contribute to climate objectives.

The budget proposal puts forward the merging of previously separate instruments, such as NDICI-Global Europe, IPA, and Humanitarian Aid, into a broader Global Europe category. **While the budget would increase from EUR 112.04 billion to EUR 176.83 billion, this blurring of specific allocations threatens to significantly reduce transparency in fund distribution.**

Moreover, the ODA-compliant spending target (funds that should align with ODA objectives) has been lowered from at least 93% to 90%. Although a 3% reduction may seem minor, in absolute terms, it represents around EUR 16.38 billion (2018 figures converted to 2025 euros using Eurostat HICP (2019-2024) and a 2.1% projected rate for 2025 as per EC Spring 2025 forecast). Additionally, this target is not permanently fixed, but could be subject to amendments by the Commission via a delegated act, adding further uncertainty ([Commission, Multiannual Financial Framework](#)).

Through the new MFF proposal, the Commission establishes that a minimum of 35% of the EU general budget shall support projects related to climate and the environment. However, the exact form this support will take remains uncertain, as does the share of Global Europe’s budget that will contribute to overall climate finance.

Flexibility appears to lead to increasing the Commission’s policy autonomy and discretionary power. The MFF programming is proposed to shift from ex ante oversight by the European Parliament and Council, with multi-annual planning and clear targets, to ex post supervision. Accountability is further reduced by vague financial programming, the removal of specific targets, and the merging of diverse expenditure categories.

Previously, main indicators guiding programmes such as NDICI were needs-based criteria, focusing on poverty, human development, crisis response, and sustainability. In contrast, the new MFF proposal introduces concepts such as shared priorities and strategic interests into the solidarity equation.

This shift grants the Commission greater discretion in decision-making, allowing it to amend programmes or prioritize EU strategic objectives over globally agreed objectives. The attempt to expand the Commission’s powers is reflected in the increase of the Global Europe cushion fund from EUR 9.5 to EUR 14.8 billion. This reserve enhances the EU’s ability to react swiftly to unexpected crises, but it also weakens budgetary predictability as well as democratic accountability. Unlike the regular budget, which is adopted by the Parliament and Council and implemented by the Commission, cushion funds give the Commission broader discretion to reallocate resources across various policy areas. ([Commission, Multiannual Financial Framework](#)).

The proposal also opens the door to a dilution of priority areas through the replacement of previously established expenditure targets by category by “full mainstream targets.” Within the Global Europe-NDICI framework, the new MFF discards clearly defined thematic targets for climate finance, meaning that climate and environmental objectives are no longer tracked as separate, enforceable allocations but are expected to be mainstreamed across all eligible programmes. While this approach may allow the Commission greater flexibility to integrate climate considerations throughout its spending, it also reduces transparency and accountability, making it harder to monitor whether Global Europe funds actually meet their climate and sustainable development objectives. In practice, mainstreaming could dilute the emphasis on climate action, as funds may be redirected toward strategic, geopolitical, or urgent priorities without clear and/or enforceable thresholds ([Commission, Multiannual Financial Framework](#)).

Finally, a clear reorientation is evident in Global Europe’s agenda, which puts the EU’s own policy and economic priorities at the core, shaping partnerships so they also serve Europe’s interests. By linking these internal and external priorities, the proposal suggests that Global Europe may primarily serve economic or security objectives, potentially leading to the sidelining of purely humanitarian, development, or climate goals. The emphasis on enhancing Europe’s visibility and maximizing its impact further implies that financial aid could be used as a soft power tool and a key instrument to strengthen the EU’s economic foreign policy.

This focus, however, may put at risk the EU’s ability to fully meet its international commitments. Prioritizing short-term geopolitical interests could undermine obligations under agreements such as the Paris Agreement, politicize international cooperation, and lead to the deprioritization of climate action, poverty reduction, and related objectives. Furthermore, changes in the structure of the MFF may make it more difficult to monitor if this is the case.

At a time of critical urgency to address climate change, as well as the disappearance of key donors from the global landscape, reducing or diluting already insufficient climate funding could seriously undermine progress toward agreed-upon global goals. Furthermore, the diminished role of parliamentary and Council oversight, while justified by the need for greater flexibility, raises serious concerns related to the transparency, accountability, and effectiveness of global funds for development and sustainability.

As outlined above, the EU’s political and strategic interests are increasingly replacing necessity-based criteria under the banner of a stronger, more competitive, and independent EU. While the Commission continues to emphasize the EU’s commitment to climate goals and the net-zero transition, climate finance appears increasingly relegated behind broader industrial, economic, and, above all, defence priorities. This shift reflects the growing geopolitical instability Europe faces, including the war in Ukraine, rising tensions with China, uncertainties in transatlantic defence cooperation, inflation, and the energy crisis, alongside internal political fragmentation and national polarization within the EU.

III. Budgetary trends across EU Member States

Budgetary trends across Member States

Country case studies from France and Germany

Key findings:

- Defence and military spending are rising significantly across EU Member States' national budgets as governments prioritize social stability, energy security, and defence in response to evolving geopolitical challenges.
- The main political parties in power within the European Union tend to prioritize economic objectives over environmental policies.
- Consequently, climate spending appears secondary for most European leaders amid the emergence of new pressing concerns.

European Union institutions are not politically independent, and their actions and priorities are shaped by negotiations and collective interests of Member States. Therefore, the EU's agenda and performance must be analysed together with that of its Member States. Recent MFF dynamics, such as the mounting of defence and military allocations, mirror similar shifts among EU Member States' national annual budgets.

Political reports analysing electoral programmes show that many parties currently participating in EU governments tend to prioritise economic concerns over climate or environmental issues. On a scale from 0 to 10 (with 10 representing a complete shift away from climate policies in favour of economic concerns), most major European political parties ranked above 6; for example, the CDU/CSU in Germany, Moderaterna in Sweden, Fratelli d'Italia in Italy, or PVV in the Netherlands. Tendencies are similar when analyzing the salience of environmental sustainability or the amount of attention and weight compared to other priorities. Except for four parties (the Dutch GroenLinks, the German Grüne, and the two major parties composing the Spanish government), the majority of parties in the European political landscape scored below 6.

Figure 3: Military expenditure by country, in current USD billions. Source: SIPRI Military Expenditure Database

Exceptionally, we find the case of Spain, where, despite the absence of strong green parties, the current governing coalition between Podemos and the PSOE leans toward environmental sustainability. This political exception to recent European trends may be explained by the fact that Spain is considered by many to be the only country in the European Union currently led by a left-wing government.

Figure 4: Parties' positions on balancing environmental sustainability and economic growth. Source: Datasets from [2019 Chapel Hill expert survey](#)

*Non-governing parties with considerable popular backing and notable representation in parliament.

*0 = supports environmental protection even at the cost of economic growth.

However, while some countries, such as Spain with the PSOE/Podemos coalition, still have climate-friendly governments, they face strong opposition on climate matters. Parties such as the Spanish Partido Popular (PP), the French Rassemblement National (RN), and the Swedish Sverigedemokraterna (SD), while not part of their national governments, hold a substantial proportion of seats and are therefore able to exert significant influence decisions regarding climate finance as well as defence and security spending.

At the Member State level, recovery and resilience plans (RRPs) under NextGenerationEU allocated a minimum of 37% to climate-related investments in 2020 (European Union). However, fiscal space is tightening due to high debt levels, rising interest rates, and the return of EU fiscal rules in 2024. Member States are reprioritizing budgets under these constraints and often redirect funds toward social stability, energy security, and defence; which, together with the ending of the NGEU allocation, may lead to a considerable diminution of climate finance per country.

Figure 5: Relative salience of environmental sustainability in the party's public stance. Source: Datasets from [2019 Chapel Hill expert survey](#)

*Non-governing parties with considerable popular backing and notable representation in parliament.

*0 = no importance, 10 = great importance.

Country case: France

France ranks 6th among the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) members, with 58.4% of its total bilateral allocable aid supporting the environment and the Rio Conventions, and 24.5% supporting biodiversity. Since 2021, it has established a Green Budget to analyze the effects of the general budget on the environment and its contribution to climate change. The data show a clear increase in positive impact in 2023; however, since then, negative and positive impacts have balanced out, returning to 2021 levels. To examine the changes between 2023 and 2025, it is useful to consider the general budget. Within this two-year period, there has been a sharp decrease in categories such as “ecology, development and sustainability” (-43%), “energy, climate and management of former mining areas” (-67%), and “public aid to development” (-36%). By contrast, defence spending rose by almost 51% over the same period, adding nearly EUR 30 billion more per year. Politically, in line with the current budgetary orientation, Macron has described the EU’s CSRD green rules as a threat to Europe’s struggling economy. Stating that “we ourselves have supported certain regulations with very good intentions but, at the moment we’re living in, we need to be able to suspend them until we’ve regained our ability to compete,” his words appear aligned not only with recent budgetary changes in France but also with the MFF’s renewed focus on competitiveness.

Country case: Germany

In Germany, the climate emergency message, once strongly present in the national political discourse after the youth-led movement of 2019, is increasingly failing to resonate with both the public and politicians. A striking example was the televised debate between CDU leader and current Chancellor Friedrich Merz and former Chancellor and SPD “Spitzenkandidat” Olaf Scholz in the run-up to the last German general election, where environmental policies barely received any attention. Merz stated in his election campaign that recent economic policy had been geared “almost exclusively” toward climate protection, which his party “will and must change.” Still, the new coalition government emerging after the election reaffirmed its commitment to the Paris Agreement and to Germany’s 2045 climate neutrality target. The new draft budget and financial planning until 2029 set record levels of government investment, including a EUR 500 billion special fund for infrastructure and climate neutrality.

So far, however, only EUR 100 billion out of this are earmarked for transfer to the Climate and Transformation Fund (KTF), a special fund dedicated to climate policy spending. Furthermore, this fund may only be considered partially as international climate finance, since its main objective is to support Germany’s transformation into a sustainable and climate-neutral economy. Although it allows for international climate protection and related environmental measures, the funding provided outside Germany will remain limited. The use of the remaining EUR 400 billion allocation rests with the government and parliament. The Greens have already warned that this flexibility could allow the CDU/CSU alliance to channel money toward climate-damaging initiatives—such as the CSU’s electoral proposal to reintroduce subsidies for agricultural diesel, the government’s retreat from its 2030 coal exit objective, or the increasing reliance on carbon pricing as the primary tool to combat global warming.

IV. Impact on international climate finance

Bilateral climate finance

Multilateral climate finance provided through MDBs

The European Investment Bank

Key findings:

- Official Development Assistance (ODA) is expected to drop by 9 to 17 % in 2025, following a 9 percent decrease in 2024.
- ODA aimed at climate finance has similarly declined, with major donors such as Germany and Sweden significantly reducing their total contributions.
- While multilateral aid is relatively stable or slightly increasing, bilateral flows show signs of decline. This resilience is explained by the fact that international, pooled projects are less vulnerable to shifts in national political agendas.
- MDB climate finance is increasing overall, but it is less concessional than ODA, offering less favorable conditions to developing countries, which risks the exacerbation of debt accumulation in recipient countries and reduces access to finance for the poorest and most fragile states.
- MDBs disproportionately prioritize climate mitigation over adaptation, creating a gap in financing vulnerability and resilience projects in developing countries.
- While total investment by MDBs such as the EIB is increasing rapidly, climate-related investment outside EU borders remains limited and stagnated.

To address Europe’s international development assistance, both bilateral and multilateral aid must be considered. Bilateral aid is provided directly from one government to another, enabling donor countries to exercise greater control over how the aid is allocated and used.

As a result, this form of aid often more strongly reflects the donor’s political, economic, or strategic interests. This pooled funding is managed collectively, enabling joint decision-making with recipient countries and technically reducing the influence of individual donors.

i. Bilateral climate finance

The stagnation of international climate finance, both at the European Union and at the national fiscal level, has had repercussions for the Official Development Assistance (ODA) budgets, a category used by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) to measure foreign aid. According to OECD recent publications, ODA is expected to drop by 9-17% in 2025, following a former 9% decrease in 2024.

The decline comes as a consequence of recent cuts by some of ODA’s major providers of the last decades: namely, France, Germany, the United Kingdom, and, most importantly, the USA. Bilateral ODA in 2027 is projected to fall almost back to 2019 levels, substantially impacting the ability of the poorest countries to address and mitigate climate change. ([OECD, Cuts in development Assistance](#))

Figure 6: EU Bilateral Aid Climate Finance to Developing Countries 2021-2024 (provided amount in EUR millions). Source: Support to developing countries - [Reporting year 2021](#), [Reporting year 2022](#), [Reporting year 2023](#), [Reporting year 2024](#), [Reporting Year 2025](#).

With more than 30% directed to climate-related projects and this share steadily rising, ODA is key for climate finance. However, following similar tendencies to the general budget, climate-related ODA has recently declined, with major donors such as Germany and Sweden reducing their total contributions. Germany's ODA net disbursements show a 23% reduction from USD 41.25 billion in 2022 to USD 31.86 billion in 2024.

While Sweden's contribution was more limited in total numbers and the decrease since 2022 amounted only to 10% of all ODA disbursement, its share of GNI has fallen to 0.79%. Although still above the OECD's recommended 0.7% of GNI on Official Development Assistance, the share strikes as the lowest on Sweden's contribution for the last 14 years ([OECD, Data Explorer](#)).

Figure 7: ODA Net Disbursement per Country (USD millions). Source: [OECD, Data Explorer](#).

While some countries, such as Belgium and Portugal, have increased their overall shares, these amounts remain limited and relatively inconsequential in the broader context. Belgium’s 10% increase since 2022 amounts to USD 301 million, Portugal’s 30% increase since 2022 corresponds to USD 147.5 million ([OECD, Data Explorer](#)). In addition, while climate-related ODA seems to perform better than general assistance, conditions for climate-related support are shifting toward larger volumes of non-grant financial instruments, such as concessional and non-concessional loans, credit lines, or similar bonds.

Notably, in Germany and Italy, climate finance within ODA is rising in general terms, but it is also **increasing the share of non-grant financial instruments** by 38.4% and 25.5%, respectively. This trend risks exacerbating debt accumulation in recipient countries and reduces access to finance for the poorest and most fragile states. While ODA-compliant projects must meet certain requirements, such as minimum concessionality, ODA is increasingly directed toward commercially viable projects, leaving critical areas such as climate adaptation (where return of investment is low or non-existent) underfunded (Reportnet).

ii. Multilateral climate finance

While bilateral ODA, provided by one country to another, remains the main channel for international development assistance overall, **the share of multilateral aid is increasing over time**, as donors emphasize pooled funding and global cooperation mechanisms.

In particular, within the EU, there is a strong tradition and institutional role for multilateral aid through EU-level institutions and international organizations.

Figure 8: Multilateral Climate Aid to developing countries per EU Member State (provided amount in EUR millions). Source: Support to developing countries - [Reporting_year 2021](#), [Reporting_year 2022](#), [Reporting_year 2023](#), [Reporting_year 2024](#), [Reporting Year 2025](#).

*Some EU Member States, such as Ireland and France, have been excluded from the analysis because its data is restricted from public view by the country.

In contrast to bilateral and regional Official Development Assistance (ODA), multilateral aid, while significantly smaller in volume than bilateral ODA, does not show a marked decline.

On the contrary, in most cases it appears to remain stable or even increase slightly. This trend may be explained by the fact that common or international projects tend to be less affected by shifts in individual countries' political or strategic priorities and take place within long-term international collaborations.

Multilateral Development Banks (MDBs) play a critical role within both multilateral climate aid and capital markets.

MDBs provide long-term, affordable financing for renewable energy, resilient infrastructure, sustainable agriculture, and disaster preparedness. Although they are publicly owned and their core resources stem from member state contributions together with bonds issued on international capital markets, they play a central role in mobilizing private capital, providing the largest share of private climate finance with 38% (Council on Foreign Relations). This characteristic gives MDBs strategic importance for climate finance. While some investments are counted within the ODA, some projects or investments are not, as they mostly include concessional grants.

MDBs rely heavily on the EU and its Member States in several interconnected ways.

In Europe-focused banks like the EIB and EBRD, the EU and its Member States' ownership gives them direct control over governance and lending priorities, and in the international sphere, European member states' political weight helps set the climate agenda, previously pushing MDBs toward Paris-aligned operations and signaling credibility to other donors and investors. A reduction in EU and Member States' support would therefore limit both the scale of climate finance and the ambition of MDB-driven climate initiatives.

In global MDBs, EU and its Member States' influence comes mainly from policy shaping and contributions to concessional funds.

These resources are crucial for financing high-risk, climate-focused projects in low-income countries and for leveraging private investment. Beyond capital subscriptions, the EU and its Member States play a critical role in concessional finance or grants, the highly subsidized resources that enable MDBs to support climate action in low-income and vulnerable countries. In the World Bank's International Development Association (IDA), EU Member States consistently rank among the top donors, collectively representing a major share of replenishments. For the African Development Fund (ADF), the concessional arm of the AfDB, EU Member States are again among the largest external contributors. Furthermore, through the Green Climate Fund, the EU and its Member States channel resources that are then blended with MDB operations, increasing the climate finance volume delivered.

According to MDBs' annual joint statements, since 2019, climate finance has more than doubled, from USD 61.6 billion to USD 136.6 billion in 2024.

Of the 2019 aggregated figure, USD 41.5 billion was committed to low- and middle-income economies, rising to USD 85.1 billion in 2024. While this appears to be a positive development, the share of allocations directed to low- and middle-income countries is progressively declining. The main explanation for this is found in the role of the EU's investment bank, the European Investment Bank (EIB), which is generally considered the largest multilateral financial institution in the world in terms of total assets and lending capacity. Member States' Development Banks generally align their climate finance activities with their respective countries' strategic priorities and global commitments.

iii. The European Investment Bank

This subsection will analyse recent trends in the EIB, not only due to its leading role in the multilateral financial sphere but also due to its almost exclusive EU/Member State constituency.

Since 2020, the EIB signed total financing has increased exponentially from EUR 61,6 billion to a total of EUR 100 billion expected in 2025, which represents a ~62% increase over six years.

Even though part of EIB finances are outside Europe, only a small fraction of those external projects are counted as “climate action” (~6%). Inside Europe, a bigger share of projects may be climate-related because EU policies prioritize the Green Deal and climate objectives, so projects in the EU are more likely to be climate-focused.

The fact that the EIB investments outside Europe are mainly related to non-climate sectors like infrastructure, industry, or energy projects that are not strictly classified as climate action gives a partial explanation for the investment shares to be decreasing in low and middle-income countries ([EIB Climate Bank Roadmap](#)).

Figure 9: EIB Investments (EUR billions). Sources:

- [European Investment Bank Financial Report 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023](#)
- [Joint report on Multilateral Development Banks 2021 and 2024](#)
- [European Investment Bank Global Impact Report 2024/2025](#)

It is important to note that financing from budgetary resources has been increasing steadily. This financing consists of capital and funds provided directly by the EIB member countries, primarily EU sovereign states. The rise in their contributions to the EIB, combined with the stagnation of climate finance for low- and middle-income countries, suggests that these funds are being directed mainly towards projects within EU countries.

Figure 10: EIB Climate Finance according to the countries' income (EUR billions). Source: [Joint report on Multilateral Development Banks 2021 and 2024](#).

For the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), although contributing considerably less finance, the 2019 shares of total allocation to low- and middle-income countries and to high-income countries remained similar, at around 9% and 5.6% respective.

As noted previously, the EU and its Member States' progressive deprioritization (as evidenced by declining ODA disbursements) of such spending contrasts with the overall increase in MDB investments. However, the funds from European MDBs tend to bypass climate-related projects outside Europe, where the majority of low- and middle-income countries are located.

Although total MDB climate investments are rising, these financial resources do not meet ODA requirements, as they mostly consist of non-concessional financial aid. Given that such investments offer less favorable conditions for recipients, they do not provide equal opportunities for developing countries to combat climate change.

This trend leaves the poorest countries and non-economically beneficial projects vulnerable and directly hinders the EU's achievement of its global commitments, undermining the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities established in the Copenhagen Accord.

Figure 11: EIB Financing (EUR billions). Source: European Investment Bank Financial Report 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024.

V. Conclusions

As public budgets are finite, an increased focus on defence and industrial policy risks crowding out climate spending. Short-term priorities, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, breaking security threats, economic shocks, new fiscal pressures constraining the budget, or the need to prepare for potential emergencies, may divert resources from long-term climate obligations, objectives, and commitments.

AN INCREASED FOCUS ON DEFENSE AND INDUSTRIAL POLICY RISKS CROWDING OUT CLIMATE SPENDING

A stronger emphasis of the European Union on defence and competitiveness could **jeopardize support for the most vulnerable countries and communities, as well as undermine Europe's decarbonization pledges.** Budget flexibility and the loss of ring-fenced allocations and reduced transparency could lead the Commission to partially disregard its international commitments and weaken accountability, impeding ex ante revision by the Parliament and the Council.

The analysis of EU budgetary trends, together with national political alignments and fiscal allocations, indicates that Europe may be following a global pattern of retreat, evidenced by ODA cuts by major donors such as the US or the UK. The simultaneous increase in defence, security, and industrial budgets has been accompanied by reductions in funding for ecological or climate-related programmes.

A stronger focus on security risks undermines support for vulnerable countries and limits their ability to withstand the growing repercussions of climate change and implement their own Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).

The European Union must integrate its global commitments as a fundamental element in building a competitive, independent, and secure Europe. Without these commitments being an integral part of every step and process, fulfilling its obligations under the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement will remain merely secondary.

It is important to notice that while overall climate financing appears to be rising, this growth mostly comes from private investors such as households or corporations, not public finance. The reduction in public or concessional finance would disproportionately affect sectors such as Agriculture, Forestry, or Land Use (AFOLU), which already struggle to attract private capital due to their lower commercial viability. Unlike energy or transport (which are dominant recipients of investment), AFOLU sectors face considerably longer return periods and higher risks. Their limited ability to attract market-rate capital makes public finance indispensable for the sectors, as without it, there is a risk of chronic underinvestment in land-based mitigation.

The consequences would be even more severe if considering the significance of the AFOLU sector in developing and emerging economies. These economies are characterised by agriculture and forestry sectors closely tied to employment, food security, and resilience. Undermining investment here risks widening social and economic inequalities, as the communities that historically contributed least to climate change would bear the uttermost loads. Ensuring sustained public climate finance for AFOLU would therefore be both a matter of justice and a sine qua non for meeting climate goals under the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement.

A move toward non-grant-based finance risks driving unsustainable debt in recipient countries and creating barriers to accessing desperately needed funds. MDB's climate finance, driven largely by a focus on commercially viable investments, does not appear to compensate for reductions in EU governments' climate finance allocations. Remarkably, while the budgetary resources of European MDBs—particularly the EIB, which largely derives funding from EU institutions and Member States—have increased exponentially, global climate-related investments have remained flat over the past five years. This suggests that climate finance flows are increasingly concentrated within Europe rather than being directed towards wider international efforts.

Autonomy and independence do not necessarily need to lead to a complete disengagement from the European Union's role as a climate finance provider for developing countries. Synergies exist, and the objectives of security and competitiveness do not necessarily conflict with climate investment, and can indeed reinforce each other. For instance, climate-related investments such as developing battery value chains or renewable energy manufacturing can support industrial policy and strengthen both economic competitiveness and green objectives.

The principles enshrined in the Green and Digital Europe initiatives, which envisioned a dual transition, could be readjusted. Competitiveness and security can advance together with the vision of a greener Europe, extending benefits not merely within the EU's borders but internationally as well.

To continue to uphold Europe's geostrategic influence and climate ambition, the EU and its Member States should continue to integrate binding climate finance targets within all budgetary and sectoral policies, not marginalize them within general budgets, as may be understood from the MFF proposal. **The European Union must demonstrate, in action as well as rhetoric, that environmental responsibility is indivisible from security, competitiveness, and global cooperation.**

Organizational profile

SLYCAN Trust is a non-profit think tank working on climate change, sustainable development, climate finance, risk management, entrepreneurship, biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, security, and social justice including gender and youth empowerment. Our work spans the national, regional, and global level from policy analysis and evidence-based research to capacity-building, technical support provision, and on-the-ground implementation.

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